

Navigating Engineering Capstone Strategies

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Abstract

Capstone is an academic project undertaken by students in their final years of an engineering program, typically a requirement for graduation and often involving external partners. This project offers a valuable opportunity to assess students' readiness for the job market by engaging them in complex projects that address real-world challenges. However, ensuring the success of such initiatives requires comprehensive support and ongoing communication among all stakeholders. This paper presents a series of pedagogical strategies for organizing a Capstone program and preparing students to handle real-life project challenges. The main goal is to ensure students understand project objectives, involve company mentors in clarifying challenges, and enable comprehensive monitoring by academic advisors. Students and advisors need a clear understanding of the project's time commitment and desired outcomes. Several strategies are developed to enhance the Capstone experience for all stakeholders involved. This Capstone program engaged 551 students and 73 companies, yielding 151 successful projects despite occasional student setbacks. Ongoing positive feedback from companies underscores the program's enduring value each semester.

Keywords: Capstone Projects; Expectation Management; Project Kick-off Readiness.

1 Introduction

The job market has changed in recent decades, and education systems should adapt to ensure the skills demanded by society are met. In this regard, engineering programs have been adjusting their curriculum, incorporating real-life projects into the classroom. These projects encompass various challenges, including communication, organization, and, of course, technical skills. This shift has become a requirement regulated by government and accreditation organizations.

In Brazil, the Ministry of Education defines a set of competencies aligned with a professional profile supported by a holistic and humanistic approach. These competencies include analytical skills, research and development of innovative solutions, entrepreneurship, teamwork, communication, among other skills. They are outlined in the National Curriculum Guidelines for Undergraduate Engineering Courses (BRASIL, 2019). These guidelines also explicitly state that engineering programs must include a final project to confirm students have developed all necessary competencies. This guideline presents a mandatory curricular component that can be interpreted as a Capstone program, with a focus aimed at solving concrete problems, whether in the productive sector or in society at large.

In the context of ABET (Accreditation Board for Engineering and Technology), a nonprofit organization that accredits college and university programs worldwide, emphasis is placed on the need for engineering programs to demonstrate that their graduates have achieved various educational outcomes. While the term "Capstone" is not explicitly mentioned, ABET requires engineering programs to provide "a culminating major design experience" (ABET, 2021), which can be also be interpreted as a Capstone project, expecting projects designed to fulfil this requirement by offering students opportunities to integrate and apply their knowledge and skills to real-world engineering problems.

This document presents the strategies implemented in the Capstone program at Inspere (Inspere, 2022), demonstrating achieved results. The Capstone Project spans one semester, during which students should

develop and apply technical and interpersonal skills in a real and highly complex situation. In this sense, we argue that the engineering courses should promote technical combined with interpersonal competencies applied in a real and complex challenge to intensify the students' formation. This project is supervised by a multidisciplinary group of advisors and mentors. This structure of the Capstone requires comprehensive support from students and ongoing communication among various stakeholders, aligning with the concept of competence, which entails transforming knowledge and skills into practical results (Spencer & Spencer, 1993).

The following sections begin with a brief review of changes in engineering education impacted by Capstone programs. Then, the capstone project in Insper is analysed in more details and the results are discussed. Finally, the conclusions are presented.

2 Professional Engineering Education in Capstone

Baena et al. (2017) defends that engineering education has a strong link with the global economy and social development, therefore its role implies impacts and is simultaneously influenced by innovation technology. In this context, it is estimated that 43% of human tasks will be performed by machines in 2027 (World Economic Forum, 2023) and the rest will be based on relational tasks (Mercer, 2023). In addition, the five most important skills for business in 2027, described by the Future of Jobs Report (World Economic Forum, 2023), are creative thinking, analytical thinking, IA and big data, and leadership and social influence.

These points show that the engineering job is changing, but at the same time is yet very important to the society. And preparing engineering for the society is challenging, especially since the number of students applying for engineering is reducing (The Economic Times, 2023), and in addition, the Anísio Teixeira National Institute of Educational Studies and Research (INEP) has shown that the dropout index in private undergraduate courses is around 20% per year in Brazil (Christo, de Resende & Kuhn, 2018).

Considering the job market challenges and the dropout index context a set of strategies have been adopted by universities to make the engineering courses more attractive and updated. One of the strategies is to adopt an active learning methodology, e.g. Project Based Learning, as the main approach during the classes to facilitate the development of students' protagonism and leadership and social influence skills (Vieira & Lima, 2019).

Capstone Project could be interpreted as a type of Project Based Learning (PBL) methodology because students, working in groups, need to demonstrate competences of investigation and design creatively solutions (Shurin, Davidovitch & Shoval, 2021). Hauhart & Grahe (2015) show that the Capstone programs are becoming more popular, they estimate that in 1970s only 3% only all academic institutions adopted this practice, while authors report an average of 66%-75% at the time of the publication. Part of this growth probably came from the accreditation process, e.g., ABET (The Accreditation Board for Engineering and Technology), and pressure from other organizations dedicated to improving engineering education, e.g., ASEE (American Society for Engineering Education).

One study conducted by Howe and Goldberg (2019) in 2015 and involved the last 25 years of engineering capstone design education and includes 522 respondents from 256 institutions shows that (Table 1).

Table 1: Interpretation of Survey on Capstone Programs in Mechanical Engineering.

Number of different disciplines	At least two different disciplines – 52% At least five different disciplines – 11%
Duration	More than 50% last for 2 consecutive semesters
Frequency meets with a faculty coach	Weekly
Topics covered	Analysis tools; CAD design; Concept Generation; Concept Selection; Creativity and Problem Solving; Decision Making; Engineering Ethics; Functional Specifications; Intellectual Property; Leadership; Optimization; Oral Communication; Project Management, Prototyping and Testing, Sketching, Standards and Regulation, Sustainability, Teamwork, Written Communication
Evaluators (high input on course grade)	Course instructor – 83% Project advisor/coacher - 36% Industry liaisons – 8% Peers – 3%
Evaluations of deliverable (Interviewees can select multiple options)	Final written report – 77% Final oral presentation – 63% Final product – 62%
Industry/government	87%
Faculty research	64%
Team size	More than 80% have between 3-5 students
Method for assigning students to teams (Interviewees can select multiple options)	Student choice - 72% Instructure choice – 48% Student skills for project – 44%

Source: Adapted by authors from Howe and Goldberg (2019)

Two contents were not considered in the study above. The first is the student's perception of the Capstone success, Rashwan et al. (2020) defends that different perspectives regarding to this are discussed in the literature, e.g. sponsor, faculty member, however the student view if the project was a success were receiving little attention. The second is the assessment rubrics and the authors argue that despite its being a common practice and most of the time following the ABET requirement, it does not emphasize enough soft skills such as teamwork effectiveness and leadership skills.

In a systematic review to investigate current efforts and practices more visible and accessible in capstone design experiences, Zheng et al. (2021) analysed studies published between 2006 and 2020 that satisfy the multidisciplinary needs from ABET. The final 36 results show that the most common focus of papers on capstone projects was related to sharing experiences or structure of one specific capstone project.

Zheng et al. (2021) suggest that the effectiveness of capstone projects as a major gap in the investigation of capstone fields once it's often not validated because of the lack of project evaluation data or results, especially in multidisciplinary capstone.

3 Capstone Project at Insper

The Capstone projects at Insper are in line with active learning strategies, where students learn by doing, with support from an experienced advisor. This approach emphasizes hands-on experience and practical application of knowledge, allowing students to gain valuable insights and skills that are directly applicable to real-world challenges. Through active participation in their projects, students not only deepen their understanding of

engineering competences but also develop critical thinking, problem-solving, and teamwork abilities essential for success in their future careers.

The beginning

Since its first edition, the capstone project at Insper has adhered to several core principles. These include instilling a sense of professional responsibility in engineering students, working within constraints such as time, budget, and personal interests, and always involving a real external client to provide authentic feedback for the project challenges (Howe & Goldberg, 2019).

Insper offers three engineering programs (computer, mechatronics, and mechanical) that are structured as five-year courses organized into semesters, with a Capstone program in the eighth semester. The first edition of the Capstone program at Insper took place in the second semester of 2018. Following the common practice observed in universities across the USA, the program had a duration of one year, organized into two consecutive semesters. Students were expected to dedicate a total of 300 hours, or 150 hours per semester in the Capstone project, allowing time for taking three elective courses in parallel with the Capstone project.

A series of weekly two-hour classes addressed pertinent topics aimed at preparing students for the challenges they might encounter during their projects, the most common topic was oriented to project management, exploring different strategies. Typically, there are approximately 12 classes, with most of the classes oriented to some activities with all the groups, and the remaining sessions dedicated to group reviews, such as team dynamics, report quality assessment, or other forms of mentoring. Additionally, students were required to visit companies once a week, typically spending several hours working in the company offices.

Students have three main assessment points that are always based on the Capstone competences: one individual assessment and another for the entire group, both evaluated by the project advisor. The third assessment is conducted by an evaluation committee composed of at least three professors. These evaluations occur in the middle of the semester and at the end of the semester.

Adjustments

The initial adjustment made to the Capstone program was transitioning from a two-semester format to a single semester. This change was implemented mainly because students often participate in internship programs during their final undergraduate year, which could lead to conflicts with the Capstone project. This change consolidates a 300-hour commitment into a semester. The dedication was later expanded and is currently 360-hour.

Another important adjustment relates to the Capstone competencies. Originally, the competencies were: technical, organization, communication, teamwork, and design & entrepreneurship. Note that 'design & entrepreneurship' was considered a single competency group. However, from the advisors' perspective, evaluating 'design & entrepreneurship' was complicated since it mixed topics that should not be combined. Therefore, this competency group was split into design and entrepreneurial attitude.

The topics covered in classes also changed. In the inaugural edition, there were four days dedicated to project management classes and two days for organizational culture classes. However, by 2024, the curriculum evolved, with only one class focusing on project management, and the content of organizational culture was restructured into sessions oriented towards Communication, Value Proposition, and Career development. Additionally, other essential classes are regularly taught each semester, including Scientific Methodology, Ethical Responsibility, Intellectual Property, Decision Making, Technical Standards, and Effective Presentations. Classes were also moved from Thursday's afternoon to Friday's morning to avoid collision with other possible elective courses that students may be interested to take.

Several other adjustments were implemented, including advisors creating orientation plans for the semesters, reorganizing and reviewing learning goals and rubrics, determining the necessary information for reports, and creating videos and posters. However, these topics are beyond the scope of this document.

For two consecutive semesters, all classes were condensed into a single week prior to the start of the projects. This attempt was made to cover all important topics before the projects began. However, this approach did not work well; students appeared visibly tired, and their concentration levels were too low. Consequently, classes reverted to the weekly model.

4 Educational Strategies

Several educational strategies were developed and implemented with Capstone students to enhance learning, organization, team dynamics, communication, among other benefits. Below is a list of some pertinent strategies employed, which could serve as valuable models for other Capstone programs.

4.1 Golden Rules

In the first class of the Insper Capstone program, students are tasked with articulating their expectations for the project in a comprehensive document. This document serves as an official reference throughout the semester, primarily focusing on fostering alignment within the team and clarifying individual commitments. Given the diverse dedication levels and interests among students involved in the project, this alignment is crucial for ensuring cohesion and progress. By formalizing and documenting these expectations, teams can cultivate a better working environment, minimizing potential frustrations among members and facilitating the planning of subsequent project milestones. This type of agreement usually encourages students to take more responsibility for their project, as they have officially written down their commitment, typically indicating a high level of dedication.

In this activity, students must answer these 3 questions:

- What are we absolutely not going to do during the Capstone?
- What will we always remember to do when facing a challenge in the Capstone?
- What is our purpose - as a team - in carrying out the Capstone?

4.2 Communication Activities

The Insper Capstone is a significant project that students dedicate themselves to for an extended period, typically around five months or one academic semester. Throughout this timeframe, students engage in weekly hour-long meetings with a mentor from the partnering company. Additionally, they receive guidance from an Insper faculty member, meeting with them for about two hours each week. An essential aspect of the project is learning to communicate effectively in different contexts, such as academic and professional settings. One of the Capstone classes is aimed at enabling students to acquire skills to navigate these varied communication styles. In this class, examples of communication are presented to the students, who must identify styles and respond with strategies for interacting with others.

4.3 Regular Week Dedication Planning

Advisors, partners, and the institution require a clear understanding of the students' regular time commitments. Therefore, a detailed allocation plan is requested and regularly updated to streamline meeting schedules and identify any lower-than-expected dedication. This is another crucial activity conducted during Capstone classes, where students' hours of dedication are discussed and monitored. The primary goal is to complete the timetable (Table 2) with the hours each team member will dedicate to the project, considering that students may have different elective courses with varying schedules. However, a minimum of 22 hours per week is

expected for the Capstone project. Subsequently, students are asked to identify the hours they will work together in the team, with a minimum requirement of 8 hours collectively every week. While this requirement may be complex due to students' individual commitments throughout the week, it serves to gauge the alignment of dedication. A significant deviation in dedication among team members or limited time slots for the entire team to work together can indicate potential teamwork issues. With this tool, problems can be identified and preventively addressed.

Table 2. Time Dedication Planning per Week.

	Monday				Tuesday				Wednesday				Thursday				Friday			
	E1	E2	E3	E4	E1	E2	E3	E4	E1	E2	E3	E4	E1	E2	E3	E4	E1	E2	E3	E4
7:30 - 9:30 hs																				
9:45 - 11:45 hs																	Capstone Class			
11:45 - 13:30 hs																				
13:30 - 15:30 hs																				
15:45 - 17:45 hs																				
18:00 - 20:00 hs (optional)																				
20:00 - 22:00 hs (optional)																				

4.4 Engineering Standards

Real engineering projects often encounter stringent regulations from various entities, including governmental bodies. It is essential for students to be well-prepared to navigate through these standards, ensuring both quality and maintainability in their projects. As part of the Capstone program, one of the proposed activities is for students to carefully evaluate the potential standards that may impact their projects. This initiative aligns directly with the core objectives of the Insper engineering program, emphasizing the importance of students comprehending the contextual environment within which their projects operate.

Given that the projects are conducted in Brazil, the primary authority defining standards within the country is the ABNT (Brazilian National Standards Organization). However, in today's globalized world, the engineering landscape transcends national boundaries. Hence, students must also be equipped to navigate international standards such as ISO (International Organization for Standardization), CEN (European Committee for Standardization), IEEE (Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers), and ASTM (American Society for Testing and Materials).

4.5 Fortnightly Reports

While students regularly meet with advisors and mentors, there is a system in place to monitor their progress and activities throughout the capstone process. Every two weeks, students are required to document how they have allocated their time to the project, detailing the tasks undertaken and the number of hours spent on each task. Although these reports are not directly evaluated, they serve as a tool for students and advisors to assess whether the progress is adequate. This practice proves very convenient for advisors during the final evaluation phase, enabling them to closely monitor each student's progress and assess the adequacy of their work. One of the identified problems was that students were reporting group work in the report, when the intention was to identify individual contributions, even if they collaborated most of the time in tasks. Therefore, there is an emphasis on the requirement to report personal contributions.

The guidance provided to students for completing the report is as follows: “Briefly describe YOUR contributions to the project, what YOUR learnings were, what skills YOU developed during this last period. If you wish, you can also make a brief reflection on how you could contribute more efficiently to the project in the coming weeks. Please indicate the approximate number of hours you have dedicated to the project since the last fortnightly report.”

5 Results

The primary source of information within the Capstone program is derived from student feedback. Students were surveyed regarding the depth of their learning experience throughout the Capstone activities. The graph below (Figure 1) illustrates data from the four most recent editions of the Capstone program.

Figure 1. How students identify their learning levels for each main competence

It is evident that teamwork emerges as the most significant perceived competency developed by students throughout the Capstone program, since students are grouped with other students and must face a longer project where many issues may arise. The main orientation passed for advisors on how to prepare students is that groups must be self-organized and self-managed, and advisors should check if the harmony of the group is efficient. As necessary, advisors have individual meetings to identify group problems. Since the implemented Capstone projects mix students from different major, many teams have students that are not used to work together, creating an additional challenge that is important for learning teamwork.

The following graph (Figure 2) presents how do groups evaluate the working dynamics of their group. This graph also shows results from the last four editions of the Capstone program.

Figure 2. How students evaluate their group dynamics

The graph clearly illustrates that while some groups encounter teamwork challenges, the majority exhibit harmony. However, there is a high expectation for students to assess their competencies in entrepreneurial attitude. Many students struggle with negotiating with stakeholders and encounter difficulties in risk planning.

There is a big challenge in the perception of importance of the regular classes taught, while the discussions in the faculty meeting leading to a consensus that the classes are important and relevant for student formation, but even in the last years students have regular feedback, around 50% of the students do not consider the classes important for their formation, while the other 50% think it is important. The results are very stable, even changing topics, professors, and weekday for the classes (Figure 3).

How do capstone classes support the development of the project? (asked to students)

Figure 3. Perception of importance of capstone classes by students

6 Conclusion

This document presents the strategies implemented in the Capstone program at Insper (Insper, 2022). With 12 editions already completed, ongoing adjustments continue to refine the program. Strategies such as the Golden Rule, where students create a document aligning their expected dedication to the project, have a direct impact on group dynamics since team members are not self-selected, and this commitment among members must be clear and as official as possible. Regular Week Dedication Planning, which enables students to plan their meetings and team activities efficiently, is another simple tool that provides a clear understanding of how each team member will dedicate time to the project. Additionally, Fortnightly Reports ensure continuous monitoring of student progress, helping to identify problems early, well before the intermediate reports, thereby improving the chances of success for both the project and the learning goals.

There are several other strategies commonly used in engineering capstone programs that are also employed in the presented program. These include the following deliverables: a planning report, individual and group reports, slides from the evaluation board, a demonstration video, a banner for the closing ceremony, and a reviewed report.

These strategies have been thoroughly tested, and upon recognition of their value by faculty, have been established as official and integral components of the Capstone program. Furthermore, the findings of Figure 1 are consistent with the literature gap Rashwan et al. (2020) discussed, as long as they cover the undergraduate perspective on the capstone. Since its not considered in the grade, it's used to improve the content and schedule.

This capstone program already had 12 editions that involved 551 students and 73 different companies, resulting in 151 projects, all of which were successfully completed, contradicting the results shown in Figure 3. The content of the capstone class was changed during the program, and the number of respondents does not reach 50% of the total number of the capstone class. Meanwhile, positive feedback from the companies underscores the program's value, which continues to be applied semester after semester. The average Net

Promoter Score (NPS) from partner companies that have concluded projects thus far is 9.31, indicating a favourable perception of the students' and projects' quality. These results are also in line with Zheng et al.'s (2021) assertion for the effectiveness analysis of the capstone projects.

Artificial Intelligence tools were used to review the text of this paper, as English is not the authors' native language. However, the tool was not used to create new content.

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